

From bronchitis to rhinosinusitis: new evidence and therapeutic horizons for Atusin® (ARINA)

Julian Rangachev¹

1 Department of Oncological Diseases in Otorhinolaryngology, Head and Neck Surgery, Queen Giovanna Hospital, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

2 ENT Department, MBAL "St. Anna – Varna" AD, Varna, Bulgaria

3 Clinic of Ear, Nose and Throat Diseases, UMHAT "St. Anna" – Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

4 Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

5 ENT Department, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Aleksandrina Topalova-Shishmanova (aleksandrina.topalova@mu-plovdiv.bg)

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Abstract

Clinical efficacy was evaluated through the ARINA trial, an open-label, prospective real-world study involving 624 patients treated with Atusin® CAP. Over a 10-day period, total symptom severity decreased by 78%, with modified SNOT-22 scores decreasing from 34.54 to 7.66 points. Significant alleviation of nasal congestion, headache, and sputum thickness was recorded consistently, regardless of whether concomitant antibiotics were administered. Quality of life improved by 81.3%, with 97.3% of participants identified as clinical responders. Adverse events were negligible, occurring in less than 2% of cases. The findings demonstrate that the multimodal action of Atusin® CAP effectively facilitates mucolysis and reduces mucosal edema. This investigation confirms that the product provides a robust clinical benefit by restoring physiological defense mechanisms, offering a reliable therapeutic strategy and comprehensive pathophysiological approach for acute rhinosinusitis in primary care.

Keywords

Atusin CAP, bromelain, essential oils, green Brazilian propolis, rhinosinusitis

Introduction

Acute rhinosinusitis (ARS) is one of the most common inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract and poses a significant challenge in both diagnosis and treatment (Fokkens et al. 2020). It usually involves a viral infection that causes inflammation of the nasal and sinus mucosa, induces mucosal edema and secretion stasis, disrupts mucociliary transport, and paves the way for secondary bacterial

superinfection (Scadding and Kariyawasam 2012; Lemien-gre et al. 2018). A vicious cycle of inflammatory reactions, hypoxia, and viscous secretion retention occurs, which maintains the process and prolongs the time to recovery (Lemien-gre et al. 2018; Fokkens et al. 2020).

ARS usually has a 1-year prevalence of 6–15% and is most commonly the consequence of a viral infection (common cold). In most cases, it is a self-limiting disease, but it can also lead to life-threatening complications, with death

also having been reported (Green et al. 2014). ARS is one of the most frequent reasons for antibiotic prescription, which makes its proper treatment a serious challenge in the face of growing antibiotic resistance worldwide (Houser and Keen 2008; Pai et al. 2023). To date, the predisposing factors for ARS are still not entirely clear, with active and passive smoking, along with concomitant chronic diseases, being among the few mentioned in the literature (Bayrakci et al. 2005; Kuruvilla and De la Morena 2013; Kashani et al. 2015). Interestingly, there is no evidence that allergies and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GORD) can lead to the onset of ARS (Khalid et al. 2010; Duraisingham et al. 2014).

The available therapeutic agents most often target only individual steps in the complex pathophysiological pathway of rhinosinusitis; therefore, they bring limited therapeutic efficacy. A 2018 Cochrane systematic assessment has shown that uncomplicated acute rhinosinusitis rarely requires routine antibiotic therapy (Lemiengre et al. 2018). Further, the data in EPOS 2020 (Fokkens et al. 2020) and the overview by Koch et al. (2016) indicate that available mucoactive and natural products achieve good results, but the evidence is heterogeneous and limited, which highlights the need for further high-quality studies. These observations reveal the need for an overall, pathogenetically targeted approach to improve mucociliary clearance, reduce inflammation, and promote mucosal function recovery.

In the present study, the efficacy of a food supplement in ameliorating ARS symptoms is evaluated. Atusin® CAP contains a combination of four purified essential oils (eucalyptus, sweet orange, lemon, and myrtle), along with bromelain and green Brazilian propolis. In a recent multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study with 310 participants, the combined product was found to be effective in the treatment of acute uncomplicated bronchitis (Petkova et al. 2025).

Essential oils are volatile plant secondary metabolites that are known for their well-pronounced antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and mucolytic activity (de Sousa et al. 2023). The main terpenes in the essential oil (EO) from *Eucalyptus globulus* are 1,8-cineole (eucalyptol), p-cymene, and α -pinene. The oil has been used in folk medicine for centuries in the treatment of respiratory conditions such as cough, sore throat, nasal congestion, bronchitis, and sinusitis (Vigo et al. 2004). In addition, its antibacterial efficacy has been shown against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (Dixit et al. 2014; Dohare et al. 2014). The essential oils from *Citrus aurantium* var. *dulcis* and *Citrus limon* are both rich in D-limonene, α - and β -pinene, and β -myrcene (Klimek-Szczykutowicz et al. 2020; Vukić et al. 2023). The EO from *Myrtus communis* contains primarily D-limonene, 1,8-cineole, and linalool (Mulas and Melis 2011). All the listed EOs exhibit mucolytic, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects (Alipour et al. 2014; Suntar et al. 2018; Arena et al. 2021).

Bromelain is a mixture of proteolytic enzymes that contains several thiol endopeptidases and is obtained from the stem and fruit of *Ananas comosus* (Chakraborty et al. 2021). Previous research has demonstrated the mucolytic,

fibrinolytic, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory activity of bromelain (Petkova et al. 2025). *In vivo* experiments showed inhibitory activity on cyclooxygenase-2 and prostaglandin E2 expression (Gaspani et al. 2002; Bhui et al. 2009), thus leading to reduced swelling in the nasal passages (Manzoor et al. 2016). It is also known to suppress mucus production and improve drainage (Chakraborty et al. 2021).

Green Brazilian propolis is a resinous mixture produced by honey bees (*Apis mellifera*). The main compounds that it contains are terpenes, cinnamic acids, flavonoids, and artemillin C—a prenylated derivative of *p*-coumaric acid (Shahinozzaman et al. 2020). Various studies showed significant anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory activity for this natural product (Machado et al. 2012; Dantas Silva et al. 2017; Dos Santos et al. 2022).

Having previously shown significant efficacy in acute bronchitis, Atusin® CAP was evaluated in a real-world investigation in patients diagnosed with ARS.

Materials and methods

Study design and population

An open-label, prospective, real-world practical trial was conducted from March to May 2025 in 84 otolaryngology practices (ENT) in Bulgaria. Verbal consent for participation was obtained from every patient. For convenience, the trial was given the acronym ARINA (Atusin real-time investigation in acute rhinosinusitis). Adults with a clinical diagnosis of acute rhinosinusitis meeting the following inclusion criteria were eligible to participate in the study:

- Nasal obstruction (congestion) or nasal secretion (anterior/postnasal secretion);
- Facial pain/severity;
- Reduction/absence of smell;
- Lack of previous treatment with mucolytics or mucoactive agents for the previous week;
- Duration of symptoms lasting no more than 12 weeks before inclusion in the monitoring;
- Inflammatory changes in the nasal cavity and sinuses.
- The exclusion criteria were:
 - Chronic rhinosinusitis;
 - Previous surgeries in the nose and sinuses area;
 - Bronchial asthma;
 - Use of intranasal corticosteroid sprays;
 - Pregnancy and breastfeeding;
 - Seasonal allergic rhinitis;
 - Deformation of the nasal septum and hypertrophy of the nasal conchae, which significantly impair nasal airflow;
 - Various systemic disorders that may affect the nose and sinuses (non-eosinophilic and eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangitis, Kartagener's syndrome—primary ciliary dyskinesia—and cystic fibrosis);
 - Immunologically related diseases (multiple sclerosis, polyarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and diabetes

mellitus), which change the natural course of the disease and affect the outcome of therapy;

- Sensitivity to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs;
- Allergic reactions to the active substances in the therapy used in this study;
- Patients using oral or local antihistamines, corticosteroids, and antibiotics at the time of inclusion in the study;
- Patients who have used sympathomimetics and mucolytics within seven days prior to the study;
- Regular smoking.

Study intervention

Atusin® is a gastro-resistant capsule containing a fixed dose of 120 mg of distillate of four types of purified essential oils in the ratio of 66:32:1:1 (79.2 mg eucalyptus, 38.4 mg sweet orange, 1.2 mg lemon, and 1.2 mg myrtle), 80 mg bromelain, and 10 mg green Brazilian propolis, in addition to excipients (microcrystalline cellulose, silicon dioxide, copovidone, and magnesium stearate). The product is manufactured in compliance with the local manufacturing guidelines and good manufacturing practices for food supplements, including Eurofins GMP, ISO 9001, ISO 22000, and HACCP.

During the study period, all patients took Atusin® CAP (3 × 2 capsules daily) for 10 days. Concomitant therapies (antibiotics, antipyretics, and saline) were allowed at the discretion of the respective researcher. Notably, combination with local corticosteroids, antihistamines, decongestants, or other mucoactive agents was not allowed.

Efficacy endpoints and statistical analysis

The primary endpoint of the trial was the reduction in overall rhinosinusitis symptom severity. The assessment was performed using a reduced version of the validated

Sinonasal Outcome Test-22 (SNOT-22) (Piccirillo et al. 2002; Hopkins et al. 2009), which included 16 clinically relevant symptoms of rhinosinusitis, and the version used in this study is referred to hereafter as the 16-item SNOT-22 (Table 1). The symptoms were rated by the researcher on a 6-point visual analog scale ranging from 0 to 5 (0 = lack of symptoms, 1 = very mild, 2 = mild, 3 = moderate, 4 = severe, 5 = possibly the most severe), with a total score of 0 to 80 points. The assessment was performed by the investigator on day 1 (visit V1) and at the visit on day 10 (visit V2).

Secondary endpoints consisted of:

1. Reduction in the intensity of the five most severe symptoms: nasal congestion, headache, cough, post-nasal discharge, and sputum thickness. Change in the score of the individual symptoms on the 16-item SNOT-22 on day 1 and day 10. The baseline was the symptom severity assessed by the researcher at visit V1 (baseline) and at the end of the trial at visit V2.
2. Quality of life—restrictions in daily activity were assessed by monitoring the change in the score of the individual symptoms: lack of a good night's sleep, waking up tired, reduced work capacity, fatigue, lower concentration, and tension/irritability as per the 16-item SNOT-22. The baseline was once again the severity of the symptoms assessed by the researcher at the time of patient inclusion at visit V1 and at the end of the monitoring at visit V2.
3. Assessment of the attending physician—response to the treatment assessed by the researcher at visit V2 using a verbal rating scale (0 = no complaints, 1 = significant improvement, 2 = no change, 3 = worsened). Participants with a score of 0 or 1 were identified as “responders”; participants with a score of 2 or 3 were identified as “non-responders.”

Table 1. Reduced 16-item SNOT-22 used in the study.

No.	Symptom	Lack of symptoms	Very mild	Mild	Moderate	Severe	Possibly the most severe
1	Facial pain/pressure (including headache)*	0	1	2	3	4	5
2	Blockage/congestion of the nose*	0	1	2	3	4	5
3	Sneezing	0	1	2	3	4	5
4	Runny nose	0	1	2	3	4	5
5	Cough*	0	1	2	3	4	5
6	Post-nasal discharge*	0	1	2	3	4	5
7	Thick nasal discharge*	0	1	2	3	4	5
8	Ear fullness	0	1	2	3	4	5
9	Loss of smell/taste	0	1	2	3	4	5
10	Lack of a good night's sleep**	0	1	2	3	4	5
11	Wake up tired**	0	1	2	3	4	5
12	Fatigue**	0	1	2	3	4	5
13	Reduced productivity**	0	1	2	3	4	5
14	Reduced concentration**	0	1	2	3	4	5
15	Frustrated/restless/irritable**	0	1	2	3	4	5
16	Emotional distress/sadness	0	1	2	3	4	5

* five main symptoms;

** used for quality-of-life evaluation.

4. Safety—all discomforts were documented by the researcher from day 1 to day 10, describing their frequency, severity, and duration.

The statistical analysis of patient data was performed using Student's *t*-test, Pearson's chi-square test, and Fisher's exact test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics.

Results

Participants

In total, 915 patients were assessed for eligibility (Fig. 1). Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 682 participants were eligible for inclusion in the trial. Subsequently, 58 participants were excluded from the efficacy and safety analysis due to eligibility violations ($n = 24$) and missing data in the research forms ($n = 34$). The remaining 624 participants (91.5%) completed the trial, and their data were analyzed for safety and efficacy.

Baseline characteristics

The majority of the participants were female (64.8%), and the mean age was 41.25 ± 12.52 years. Antibiotic therapy was prescribed to 46% of the included patients, with an average duration of 7.52 ± 1.85 days. The frequency of prescription of the different classes of antibiotics was as follows: cephalosporins (34.3%), broad-spectrum penicillins (24.6%), quinolones (19.0%), macrolides (11.8%), and lincosamides (8.3%). Tetracyclines, aminoglycosides, and sulfonamides were administered to only 2.1% of the participants. The remaining participants (54%) were not prescribed antibiotic treatment. Isotonic saline solutions were included in the therapy of 45% of the participants.

Primary endpoints: Reduction in the total severity of rhinosinusitis symptoms

The total severity of rhinosinusitis symptoms at the beginning of treatment (day 1) using the 16-item SNOT-22 was estimated at 34.54 ± 13.532 points, whereas at the end of treatment (day 10), it was 7.66 ± 9.63 points. The reduction in the severity of symptoms was, on average, 26.89 points, or 78% ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 2).

Given that therapy in 46% of the monitored patients included an antibiotic, the reduction in the total severity of rhinosinusitis symptoms was also presented by therapeutic group (with antibiotic/without antibiotic): Group 1 (Atusin® CAP + antibiotic) and Group 2 (Atusin® CAP). At the beginning of treatment (day 1), in Group 1, the total severity of rhinosinusitis symptoms was estimated at 37.3 points and differed significantly from that in Group 2, 32.1 points ($p < 0.001$), which confirmed the physicians' decision to include an antibiotic. At the end of treatment (day 10), there was no difference in the reduction of the

Figure 1. Participants' distribution scheme.

Figure 2. Total severity of symptoms in points, based on the 16-item SNOT-22 analysis.

Table 2. Results at day 1 and day 10 with and without antibiotic therapy.

	Day 1	Day 10	<i>p</i> -value*
Group with antibiotic	37.3	7.83	<0.001
Group without antibiotic	32.1	7.64	0.804
<i>p</i> -value*	<0.001	<0.001	

**t*-test.

total severity of symptoms, regardless of antibiotic use. In Group 1, the total severity of rhinosinusitis symptoms was estimated at 7.83 points, compared to 7.64 points in Group 2 ($p = 0.804$) (Table 2).

Secondary endpoints: reduction in the intensity of the five most severe symptoms

The studied therapy reduced the intensity of the five most severe symptoms for the participants by 75%, or an average of 11.05 ± 4.81 points ($p < 0.001$). At the beginning of the trial (day 1), the severity was estimated at 14.64 ± 4.37 points, compared to 3.59 ± 3.78 points at the end of the trial (day 10) (Fig. 3).

The same correlation was observed separately for each of the monitored symptoms, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Reduction in the intensity of the monitored symptoms.

Symptom	Day 1	Day 10	% reduction	p-value*
Blockage/congestion of the nose	3.7	1.0	72.1% ↓	< 0.001
Facial pain/pressure	2.6	0.5	80.3% ↓	< 0.001
Cough	2.2	0.6	74.6% ↓	< 0.001
Post-nasal discharge	3.1	0.9	71.9% ↓	< 0.001
Thick nasal discharge	2.9	0.6	79.9% ↓	< 0.001

*t-test.

Reduction in the intensity of the five most severe symptoms by group (with/without antibiotic therapy)

Regardless of antibiotic administration, the five most severe symptoms of rhinosinusitis were statistically significantly reduced in both groups ($p < 0.001$), as shown in Table 4.

The correlation was further observed with statistical significance for each of the monitored symptoms in both groups (Table 5).

Quality of life

A significantly lower score on the 16-item SNOT-22 indicated better quality of life regarding the impact of rhinosinusitis symptoms on daily activities. Taking into account the overall trial period, the average quality of life improved by 81.3%. At the end of the trial (day 10), participants reported statistically significantly better quality of life (reduced SNOT-22 score = 0.3) compared to the beginning of the trial (day 1) (reduced SNOT-22 score = 1.6) ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 4).

Assessment of the attending physician

Overall, 97.3% of all participants responded to the treatment and were assessed by the researchers as “cured” or “improved.”

Safety

During the trial, no serious adverse reactions were reported. Mild adverse events (stomach discomfort) occurred in less than 2% of the participants and did not require discontinuation.

Discussion

This open-label, prospective, practical trial presented the first time that Atusin® CAP, a food supplement containing a combination of valuable natural products, was tested for its safety and efficacy in patients with rhinosinusitis. The results from ARINA demonstrated that it exhibited significant clinical benefit within 10 days, while many published studies on acute rhinosinusitis treatment reported an average recovery time of 14 days (Scadding and Kariyawasam 2012; Fokkens et al. 2020). In addition, the results indicated a comparable time to recovery in patients with and without antibiotic treatment. This finding is especially

Table 4. Reduction in the total intensity of the five most severe symptoms in the two studied groups.

Participants	Day 1	Day 10	% reduction	p-value*
Group 1 (Atusin + antibiotic)	15.8	3.8	75.9% ↓	< 0.001
Group 2 (Atusin)	13.6	3.5	74.3% ↓	< 0.001

*t-test.

Figure 4. Quality of life improvement expressed by reduction in points (16-item SNOT-22).

important given the fact that antibiotic resistance has increased markedly in the last decade (Brüssow 2024).

The data obtained in this study are consistent with a recently published double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel study of Atusin® CAP in patients with acute bronchitis (AABA). The AABA (*Atusin in Acute Bronchitis in Adults*) trial proved the efficacy of the studied therapy in rapidly reducing cough episodes and severity as well as bronchial

Table 5. Symptom alleviation in both groups (Atusin® CAP with/without an antibiotic).

Symptom	Group 1 (Atusin + antibiotic)			Group 2 (Atusin)			p-value*
	Day 1	Day 10	% reduction	Day 1	Day 10	% reduction	
Blockage/congestion of nose	3.81	1.07	71.9% ↓	3.58	1.00	72.1% ↓	<0.001
Facial pain/pressure	3.09	0.62	79.9% ↓	2.24	0.48	78.6% ↓	<0.001
Cough	2.47	0.57	76.9% ↓	2.04	0.57	72.1% ↓	<0.001
Post-nasal discharge	3.26	0.92	71.8% ↓	3.03	0.85	71.9% ↓	<0.001
Thick nasal discharge	3.19	0.65	79.6% ↓	2.72	0.59	78.3% ↓	<0.001

secretions. Clinical benefit was observed as early as day 3 from the start of treatment, and it was maintained until the end of the study (day 10) (Petkova et al. 2025).

The results from both ARINA and AABA highlight the consistency of the effects of Atusin® CAP administration—a rapid mucolytic and anti-inflammatory response in both the lower and upper airways. These findings support the hypothesis that the mechanism of action of Atusin® CAP—targeting viscous secretion, edema, and inflammation—may also be applicable in upper airway inflammation, where the pathophysiological cascade is analogous to that of lower airway infections (Hopkins et al. 2009; Bachert et al. 2023). Interestingly, in both trials, the time to clinical improvement was rather short, the reduction of symptoms was significant (approximately 75–80%), and the safety profile was excellent.

The clinical efficacy can be explained by the complex composition of the therapy, including biologically active compounds that are well proven in practice (Chakraborty et al. 2021; Dos Santos et al. 2022; de Sousa et al. 2023). The activity of Atusin® CAP is expressed in facilitated mucolysis and alleviated edema, which could promote the restoration of normal mucosal physiology throughout the bronchial tree. Notably, Atusin® CAP is the first gastro-resistant formulation combining bromelain, green Brazilian propolis, and essential oils in a stabilized dry form, providing synergistic mucoactive, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory effects. Such a fixed combination is not currently available on the pharmaceutical market for the treatment of acute rhinosinusitis and likely underlies the rapid and improved clinical response observed in ARINA.

The ARINA study offers dual utility in the context of airway infection treatment:

- Verifies that pathophysiologically oriented approaches aimed at restoring mucociliary clearance and eliminating secretions may shorten the time to clinical improvement (Scadding and Kariyawasam 2012);
- Provides data that are relevant to real-world practice and affirms the place of Atusin® CAP in the treatment of acute rhinosinusitis with predominantly viscous secretions and difficult drainage.

The studied therapy can be used alone in uncomplicated forms of ARS or as an addition to antibiotic therapy, where the objective is to accelerate the restoration of mucociliary clearance (Werkhäuser et al. 2023; Matl et al. 2025).

In general, the data obtained from the ARINA study could facilitate further development of new therapeutic approaches for the treatment of acute rhinosinusitis. This entails a strategic shift from empirical antibiotic therapy toward a multimodal focus on restoring the mucosa's physiological defense mechanisms. Such an approach likely represents the trajectory for future clinical guidelines and research in the coming years.

Conclusion

The investigated combination (Atusin® CAP) demonstrated statistically significant efficacy in patients with acute rhinosinusitis. A marked clinical improvement in symptoms was recorded by day 10, with results remaining robust and consistent irrespective of whether the treatment regimen included concomitant antibiotic therapy. Consequently, these findings highlight the therapeutic potential of this multimodal approach in restoring normal mucosal physiology and optimizing patient recovery in the primary care setting.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: As this is not a registered clinical trial but rather a real-world observational study, informed consent was obtained verbally. No formal clinical trial procedures were conducted. The study reflects outcomes following the intake of a known product without the inclusion of a placebo control group.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Julian Rangachev <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0531-7276>

Galen Shivarov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0730-5777>

Ivan Stambolov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0198-3438>

Aleksandrina Topalova-Shishmanova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3197-365X>

Stanislav Yordanov <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9145-7235>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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